

Concept for Setting up a Working Group in the NFDI Section “Common Infrastructures”

Name of the working group

Data Science & AI

Acronym

DSAI

Contact (persons)

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Abstract

Due to the nature of NFDI as a science-led, interdisciplinary community aiming to promote systematic access to research data with the aim for them to become FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and form parts of dynamic constellations, the WG on Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DSAI) aims to coordinate and facilitate project-wide collaboration. We do so by taking advantage of the cross-cutting topics centered on technical, legal and ethical and governance of research data which have been subject of on-going discussions amongst NFDI consortia in the last year and for which a far-reaching consensus has been acquired.

Motivation and Objectives

The goals of this WG are threefold and are briefly presented below:

1. Inputs and insights

DSAI WG aims to provide tangible and measurable inputs that will result into synergies, at a first level amongst the participating NFDI projects, and at a second level for the cross-cutting topics of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and in particular for the areas of:

- Technical infrastructure (addressed topics 1 'Research Data Commons' and 5 'Infrastructure / Interoperability / Interfaces')
- Legal and ethical aspects (both topics 7 and 8 regarding 'Ethical & Legal Aspects in general' and 'Ethical-legal aspects - person-related' respectively) and to a lesser, though significant extent to the area of
- Collaborative governance framework (addressed topics 11 'Common Vision and Strategy', 12 'Cultural change', 13 'Governance and Sustainability', 15 'Internationalization' and 16 for 'Policy Advice and Consultation').

To this, we shall build upon services that are planned to be developed, operated, and provided by the NFDI4DS Consortium and aim to foster a 'fully open, community-driven research data infrastructure'. In particular, this relates to services for 'User engagement and scale-up' that aim to boost the existing user communities (such as from the 1st and 2nd 'waves' of NFDI consortia) while also remaining open to attract new ones from the next 'waves' to facilitate the widest possible take-up.

2. Consolidation

DSAI WG aims to consolidate policies (in terms of offering the governing framework), practices (that reflect and / or comply with the respective policies), and services (that combine business and technical aspects to implement the practices) for improving FAIRness of Data Science artifacts including research datasets, guidelines, machine learning models, and research software (code and executables).

To this, we shall promote infrastructures to collect and share Digital Objects that shall not only ensure the input of the DSAI solutions as FAIR, but also the output generated from these solutions following a 'FAIR in FAIR out' rationale, which shall be accompanied by the necessary benchmarking and practice assessment services. Especially for the use and implementation of benchmarking platforms, cooperation and continuous exchange amongst the participating WG projects is planned, facilitating sharing, reuse, transparency, and benchmarking of all DS and AI assets. Existing tools, such as F-UJI¹, developed by NFDI members will be reused to evaluate the FAIR compliance of the objects.

¹ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

3. Communication and promotion of transfer and scale-up of results

Finally, DSAI WG aims to help improve and increase *structured understanding* (e.g. in terms of hands-on adoption and practice-orientation) of the underlying drivers of concrete and effective interventions to increase reproducibility of the results of the participating NFDI projects. Where possible also by means of showcasing effective solutions, policy-, technical- and practice-based to end user communities. To this reason we shall promote discussion and exchange of views on the following core concepts for NFDI-wide services:

- Data bias mitigation service with application on ethics and FAIRness ('concept owner': Uni Cologne)
- FAIR Data Science Lifecycle Registries in the form of FAIR Digital Objects registries as a reusable service for all NFDI projects ('concept owner': Uni Cologne)
- FAIRness evaluation services: evaluate the FAIRness level of the digital objects with FAIRness metrics ('concept owner' : Fraunhofer FIT)
- FAIR-based benchmarking platform for DS & AI algorithms of different disciplines and application fields ('concept owner' : Uni Hamburg)
- 1-Click Online Reproducible Data Analysis: JupyterHub with Binder import and batch processing for larger binder-ready FAIR Digital Objects in cooperation with the Jupyter community ('concept owner' : GESIS)

Results of the collaboration process will be shared openly within the NFDI community.

Work Plan

All three milestones presented below are meant to provide inputs and value, apart from the participating NFDI consortia, also to the NFDI 'Basic Services' (Basisdienste). For this, there will be an increased need for coordination in order to support the choice of a concrete technical implementation.

Care will be taken so that these contributions will be distinct from those services that the participating projects are to provide themselves as part of the overall structure of the NFDI.

M1: Analysis of Commonalities for DSAI among different NFDIs (Q4 2022)

For meeting this first milestone we shall take as the main departing point the maturity and relevance of the WG DSAI offerings from the participating NFDI consortia. In particular we shall explore two aspects: (i) The relation of the needs of the constituent partners and potential for embedding to the portfolio of the NFDI basic services; and (ii) The potential for involvement of relevant partners from other NFDI consortia (both existing ones of the 1st and 2nd 'wave' as well as from the 3rd 'wave'). For the completion of this Milestone the leading questions to be explored and consensually addressed within the Working Group DSAI relate to the specific needs to be met by the offerings we shall promote and, also same importantly, how the end users of these services will be identified and engaged in order to reach the highest possible level of acceptance among the relevant end user communities. To this aim we shall apply basic principles of design thinking methodology to portray both the problem and the solutions spaces.

M2: Involvement of new NFDI Consortia (Q1/2 2023)

WG DSAI shall aim to keep an open channel with future NFDI consortia that will come as a result of the 3rd 'wave'. This Milestone shall aim to take care for the coherence of the WG offerings so that, on the one hand, (i) the new, subject-oriented NFDI consortia shall be able to take advantage and exploit

of the WG DSAI offerings in both a sustainable and interdisciplinary way, while (ii) allow for synergies between them and the existing consortia that participate in WG DSAI, and (iii) help broaden the base of the considered offerings by examining which fundamental infrastructural services need to be provided and whether / how scalability issues are addressed.

M3 Consolidation, Implementation Guidelines and Recommendations for Future Work (Q4 2023)

The DSAI working group will facilitate the development of the technological foundation for data integration within NFDI while ensuring FAIR data principles, offer reference implementations and adapt existing tools, and conduct user stories to reveal the great benefits of integrating physically and virtually heterogeneous data sources within NFDI. In order to achieve these goals, we will follow an agile approach to introducing data integration iteratively rather than in a top-down manner.

For the legacy of the WG we shall provide as part of milestone M3 access to a set of DS and AI researchers' stories and open issues that we have addressed during the two years of the operation of the WG.

Collaboration Plan

The DSAI working group will collaborate with various institutions and organizations in the fields of Data Science and Artificial Intelligence to ensure that the promoted offerings will comply with existing and future developments in the field. Apart from the collaboration we shall seek with existing NFDI consortia, we shall foster openness for new consortia as well as initiatives outside NFDI such as CESSDA, GWDG or EGI.

For our collaboration plan and in order to meet the requirements of the devised work plan there are three dimensions:

1. Integration of a mixed approach comprising both methodical research as well as carrying out experiments
2. Promoting synthesis between technical and other aspects such as ethical or legal. For this, we shall promote a deeper discussion related to the achievement of interoperability through DS and AI infrastructures and interfaces, as well as through the linkage of the various infrastructures
3. Need to create wider-scale visibility of DS and AI topics in a cross-thematic manner that affects all participating NFDI projects and consortia, supporting the need for synergies to be not only established but also used.

Initial Membership List

(Members from at least 6 institutions and at least 6 consortia)

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